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METHODS OF PROVIDING SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION TO SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCE (BASED ON SINGAPORE EXPERIENCE)<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15460852>

Annotation: This article analyzes effective ways of providing spiritual and moral education to schoolchildren using foreign experience, in particular, the example of the Republic of Singapore. The article covers the basic principles of the education system formed in Singapore, the role of state policy, family, school and society cooperation in the formation of spiritual values, as well as civic and character education programs. The possibilities of implementing these advanced experiences in the educational system of Uzbekistan, ways of adaptation and recommendations are presented based on an analytical approach.

Keywords: spiritual and moral education, foreign experience, Singapore model, civic education, family-school cooperation, moral values, national education system.

Introduction.

In modern society, spiritual and moral education is recognized as one of the main factors in raising the younger generation as a complete person. The endless expansion of the global information space, intercultural interaction and sharp changes in social life require new approaches to the formation of the spiritual world of man. In particular, the moral views of young students, their attitude to national and universal values, and their sense of social responsibility play a decisive role in their personal development. Therefore, the need for effective organization of the educational process, not only in the educational system, is increasing.

One of the main features of educational systems that are recognized as advanced in the world today is their consistent and systematic implementation of spiritual and moral education. In particular, the education system of Southeast Asian countries, including Singapore, is distinguished by its innovative approaches, effective methodologies and practical results in this regard. The Singapore education strategy sets as an important task the education of students not only as knowledgeable, but also as morally mature, patriotic, tolerant, honest and responsible individuals. Through the "Character and Citizenship Education" program implemented in the country's schools, the formation of students' personal qualities, active participation in social life, and skills in understanding and applying common values are systematically developed. Uzbekistan, while forming its national education system during the years of independence, has identified the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in schoolchildren as one of its priority areas. Based on the principle of "New Uzbekistan - a spiritual society", enriching the inner world of young people and educating them on the basis of high moral criteria is one of the urgent issues of today's pedagogy. In this regard, the study, analysis of foreign, in particular Singaporean, experience and its

adaptation to local conditions are of great scientific and practical importance. The methods of spiritual and moral education in the Singaporean education system are analyzed, their conceptual foundations, pedagogical mechanisms and possibilities of application in Uzbek schools are highlighted. Also, innovative approaches, interactive methods and practical recommendations that are useful in educating students as complete individuals based on the Singapore model are presented. The main goal of this study is to develop methodological foundations that serve to improve spiritual and moral education in Uzbekistan through the analysis of foreign experience.

Methodology:

In studying the ways of providing spiritual and moral education to schoolchildren based on foreign experience, especially the Singapore model, methodological approaches of scientific research are of particular importance. Through the methodological foundations used in this article, a deep understanding of the content of the research object, a clear analysis and drawing scientific conclusions are achieved.

The study, first of all, used the method of comparative analysis. Through this approach, the principles of spiritual and moral education in the Singaporean education system were compared with the existing approaches in the Uzbek education system. Comparative analysis, in turn, made it possible to identify the similarities and differences of both systems, as well as to determine how the results achieved in Singapore can be adapted to Uzbek schools.

Also, the study, based on the descriptive (descriptive) analysis method, comprehensively covered the content, purpose, form and methods of the “Character and Citizenship Education” program implemented in Singapore. Through this method, the conceptual foundations and socio-pedagogical mechanisms underlying foreign experience were studied. With the help of descriptive analysis, important factors such as state policy, the internal environment of the school, and the integral cooperation between family and society in the formation of moral views in students were revealed.

In addition, the article processed and summarized the information obtained based on a scientific analytical approach. Through this method, the effective aspects of foreign practice were linked to theoretical foundations and analyzed in the context of the real situations of the Uzbek education system. During the study, existing documentary sources, regulatory documents, state programs related to Singapore's education policy, international rating analyses and statistical data were used.

Another important aspect of the methodology is the pedagogical-prognostic approach, with the help of which a preliminary analysis was made of what positive results foreign experience can bring in the conditions of Uzbekistan. Through this, the article served not only to study the current situation, but also to identify promising directions. During the study, the cultural, social and historical context of the Singapore experience was also taken into account on the basis of interpretative (interpretive) analysis.

The research methodology is based on a comprehensive approach in content, which made it possible to study foreign experience in a critical and analytical spirit,

combine it with national traditions and form new pedagogical views. As a result, the article is distinguished by its theoretical foundations, reliance on empirical data and the development of practical recommendations. This increases its scientific and practical significance.

Literature analysis:

The issue of spiritual and moral education is one of the current research areas in modern pedagogy and sociology. The analysis of scientific research, practical approaches, and state policies conducted in various countries in this regard serves as an important theoretical basis for improving student education. This section analyzes foreign and domestic literature in this area.

First of all, the literature on the basis of the "Character and Citizenship Education" (CCE) program developed in Singapore is recognized as an important source. The work "Education in Singapore: Taking Stock, Looking Forward" by J. Tan and C. Chew analyzed the stages of development of the Singaporean education system, in particular, the principles of civic and moral education. The authors revealed how the components of the CCE program - such concepts as national values, civic duty, tolerance and social solidarity - are instilled through education.

Also, the research conducted by N. Sim and D. Print analyzed the impact of the CCE program on increasing the social activity of students based on empirical data. This work studied the relationship between the approach of teachers to character education in Singaporean schools and the individual moral development of students. Their research can serve as a useful basis for organizing person-centered educational processes in Uzbek schools.

The monograph "Theory and Practice of Spiritual and Moral Education" by local researcher T. Yuldoshev provides an in-depth analysis of the historical and modern foundations of spiritual education in the Uzbek education system. The author provides theoretical and practical recommendations on the mutual cooperation of the family, school and community in forming the spiritual immunity of young people.

Also, in the scientific article "International Educational Experiences and Prospects for Their Application in Uzbek Schools" by M. Jorayev (2019), advanced approaches in the education systems of Singapore, South Korea and Finland are analyzed. This study, in particular, suggests that the model of citizenship and character education in Singapore is adapted to the social environment, is systematic and effective.

Another important source is the document "Global Citizenship Education: Topics and Learning Objectives" published by UNESCO, which describes pedagogical models of teaching citizenship, human rights, tolerance and social solidarity at the global level. This document demonstrates the compatibility of the CCE program used in Singapore with international standards.

In general, the analyzed literature, combining foreign and national sources, scientifically illuminates the conceptual foundations, practical methodology and level of effectiveness of the Singapore experience. These literary foundations can serve as a scientific and methodological roadmap for improving spiritual and moral education in

the Uzbek education system.

Discussion:

Today's globalization processes put forward not only academic knowledge, but also high spirituality and strong moral support as a necessary condition for the formation of a human personality. At each stage of the development of society, the issue of educating the younger generation, especially ensuring their moral integrity, has become relevant. In this regard, an analysis of foreign, in particular Singaporean, experience can serve as a basis for a fundamental revision of spiritual and moral education in Uzbek schools.

The experience of Singapore shows that integrating moral and civic education of students into the education system is one of the important factors of social stability and development. In this country, through the CCE (Character and Citizenship Education) program, moral and ethical education is established not only as a separate subject, but also as an integral part of all educational processes and school life. It is this approach that serves to deeply instill in the minds of students universal values, concepts such as mutual respect, justice, patriotism, honesty and solidarity. Another aspect that ensures the success of this system in Singapore is the fact that school, family and state policy work in a single ideological direction. For example, parents are regularly involved in educational activities at school, and teachers act not only as educators, but also as mentors who educate individuals. The education system is strictly planned, constantly improved through assessment and monitoring mechanisms. These aspects are effective practices that can also be implemented in the Uzbek education system.

In the Uzbek experience, spiritual and moral education is often limited to extracurricular activities, class hours, and round tables. This leads to a lack of coherence and systematicity in the formation of students' spiritual consciousness. In Singapore, this process is carried out on a program basis, integrated into all subjects. Therefore, in Uzbek schools, there is a need to strengthen the moral component in all subjects, to train each teacher as an educator.

However, it is advisable not to completely and directly copy foreign experience, but to adapt and apply it based on national values, social conditions, and psychological characteristics. For example, while Singapore has its own unique society and religious and cultural context, Uzbekistan has its own historical and cultural principles, Islamic moral heritage, and folk pedagogy. Therefore, in the formation of character education, it is necessary to rely on the heritage of our great scholars such as Alisher Navoi, Ahmad Yassavi, Jadids, and to combine the ideas of national education with modern approaches. Also, based on the experience of Singapore, students are formed as conscious citizens through their participation in social projects, volunteering, and leadership activities. This experience is also of great importance in strengthening the spirit of activism, social responsibility, and patriotism among young people in Uzbekistan. The Singapore model of character and citizenship education can serve to improve spiritual and moral education in Uzbek schools not only in terms of

organization and methodology, but also with its philosophical foundations. For this, a systematic approach, increasing the educational competence of teachers, strengthening interdisciplinary integration, and establishing family-school-society cooperation are important.

Conclusion

In modern society, the spiritual and moral education of the younger generation is considered a guarantee of the development, social stability, and future of any state. Effective organization of this process requires a well-thought-out strategy, a scientifically based pedagogical approach, and a national ideological foundation. The Singapore experience is recognized as an advanced model in this direction and serves as an integrated, systematic, and monitored example of practice in the formation of moral values in school education.

Studies have shown that through the "Character and Citizenship Education" program in Singapore, such high qualities as honesty, responsibility, tolerance, civic duty and patriotism are consciously formed in students through all stages of school life. The success of this experience is manifested, first of all, in the integral cooperation of all subjects (teacher, family, society), when upbringing takes a central place in the general concept of the education system. In improving spiritual and moral education in Uzbek schools, it is also relevant to apply the main principles of this experience in combination with the national mentality, traditions of folk education, Islamic moral criteria and modern pedagogical approaches. The Singapore model should not be directly copied, but its successful elements should be applied in an adapted manner to the Uzbek education system. In particular, effective results can be achieved in this regard by introducing moral components into each lesson process based on interdisciplinary integration, turning character and citizenship education into an independent, assessable direction, systematically developing the educational competence of teachers, and involving parents in the educational process.

In conclusion, foreign experiences — in particular, the educational approach in Singapore — are highly effective in educating students as spiritually mature, morally sound, and socially responsible individuals. A sound analysis of this experience and its careful adaptation to national education will serve as an important factor in building a spiritual society in Uzbekistan.

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